

TERMINOLOGY SYSTEM OF HYDRAULIC ENGINEERING

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Annotation: The study of lexical units of the language of the specialty "Hydraulic Engineering" is presented on the basis of a sample of dictionaries, textbooks, articles, regulations and scientific and journalistic texts. The purpose of the study is to propose a thematic and derivational classification of hydraulic engineering terms for building a model of a terminological system. The multidimensionality of the hydrotechnical profile is noted, including construction, hydrology and ecology, as well as those associated with biology, energy, shipping, agriculture and other branches of science and practice.

Keywords: term, term system, concept, morphological structure, hydro-technical terminology.

INTRODUCTION

There is a sufficient number of scientific papers devoted to both theoretical and practical research of the term, terminology, terminological system and term field of various branches of science and production activities. There are a number of studies of terminological units related to certain areas of activity, both on the basis of the Russian language and in comparison with other languages. For example, medical terminology, marketing terminology, computer technology, oil business, sports terminology, legal terminology, etc. have been studied.

However, the language of the hydraulic engineering industry has been little studied, which determines the relevance of this study. The purpose of the study was to describe hydraulic engineering terms, their systematization, presentation of

the model of the term system of hydraulic engineering, identification of the features of the functioning of this term system, which, of course, can be defined as multi-core or polycentric. The study of the evolution of the terminological system of hydraulic engineering made it possible to discover the semantic connections of individual terminological units with the words of the general literary language and with dialectisms. The term is considered as an ambivalent unit that belongs both to the language system as a whole and to the terminological system of a certain scientific field. The identification of such relationships is undoubtedly important for the standardization of terms, their lexicographic representation and in the practice of technical translation and teaching the language of a specialty.

METHODOLOGY

A term field or a multi-level classification structure unified on a systematic basis, which is formed by the terms of any field of activity within a certain industry, is revealed in each term system. It should be noted that this study considers the horizontal structure of term fields that are components of the hydrotechnical term system. According to the researchers, both the term system and the term field of a certain industry can also be ordered in the form of a structure that has a core and periphery. The core contains refined specific names belonging to a given field of activity, and within the core, several independent sections can be distinguished - microfields. The periphery includes more abstract and intersectoral concepts. However, term fields do not always have clear boundaries; several term fields may intersect and overlap, and not only in the region of the periphery, but also in the region of nuclei; a term can be included in various term fields. There are two main models in the descriptions of terminological systems in various industries.

1. Single core model. Researchers of telecommunication terminology have built a model of the terminological system of this industry, highlighting in it a single four-component core and periphery.

2. Multi-core model. According to A.Z. Abdurakhmanova terminological system of construction is represented by a set of construction and interdisciplinary terms from the field of chemistry, physics, mathematics, materials science, management, that is, it combines several term fields - areas of interaction of terms from different fields of knowledge.

The term system of hydraulic engineering includes terms and term fields of related specialties, such as hydrology, hydromelioration, safe operation of hydrotechnical systems, ecology, construction, shipping, etc. Note that in addition to terms, on the periphery of the term fields of various branches of activity, there may be other units, such as professionalisms, terminoids; prototerms; preterms.

RESEARCH RESULTS

For this study, a selection of terminological units was made from special dictionaries, reference books, textbooks, articles, regulations and scientific and journalistic texts on hydraulic engineering topics. Thus, 190 frequently used terms of the educational thesaurus of the language of the specialty "Hydraulic Engineering" were selected. Based on the selected units, we will present a fragment of the system of hydrotechnical terms. Note that the list is easily extended by phrases with terminological derivatives, which in turn are also terms.

For example:

glacier - food - glacial food;

sprinkling - installation - sprinkling installation;

irrigation - canal - irrigation canal;

arch - dam - arch dam.

The list does not include verbs, since their terminological status is controversial.

In our opinion, some verbs, along with nouns and nominative phrases, can

complement the terminological system, being part of terminological fields, for example, hydrology: flow out, flow, run into, merge, overflow, meander, dry up. Processes in ecosystems can be denoted by both nouns and verbs: overgrow / overgrowth, silt / silt, swamp / swamp, etc.

It is customary to refer to the category of terms nouns in the singular: dam, water park, ice cutter; less often nominative combinations with a noun: hydroelectric power station, nuclear power plant cooling pond. However, a number of terms are used predominantly in the plural. This happens, as a rule, if the object named by the term has a large number of varieties, for example, soils, lime-stones, polymers, etc. Possible lexicalization of the plural form: water - all the water resources of the Earth, in contrast to: water - inorganic matter.

The system of hydrotechnical terms of the language refers to the "old" term systems, the origins of which go back to ancient times. This fact explains the emergence of a large number of prototerminals in the hydrology subsystem, which subsequently, having passed into the category of terms, they did not lose their semantic connection with etymon. Thus, the lexico-semantic variants of a polysemantic word can function in the language both as terms and as lexical units of the general literary language: river, sea, lake, oxbow lake, source, wave, swamp, etc. Let us give examples of functioning these units as terms and words of the general literary language, often with figurative meanings. Consider the various interpretations of the word swamp.

In the XX century. the thesaurus of hydrotechnical terminology was replenished with units of the energy term field: hydroelectric power station, nuclear power plant cooling pond, etc. Large-scale studies of the role of water bodies in ecosystems were carried out, and the dictionary was enriched with terms of ecology, biology, chemistry and other sciences.

Perhaps the most active process of replenishing the hydrotechnical dictionary can be considered derivation. Let's single out the following ways of word formation:

- Prepositional: run in, flow out;
- suffixed: meander, oxbow lake, glacier;
- prefixed-suffixal (including those with zero suffixation): source, inflow, deposit, salinization, stocking with fish;
- composition: spillway, freeze-up, breakwater, sludge drifter;
- combined methods of word formation: spillway, spillway, water-retaining, water-semi-permeable.

A quantitative analysis of the sample shows that the number of foreign borrowings (meander, fairway, delta, dam, polymer, drain, etc.). And words with international derivational elements (hydro-, electro-, mini-) are relatively small. To a much greater extent, term formation in the field of hydraulic engineering is realized due to the crystallization of the meanings of pre-terms and proto-terms, metaphorization, as well as the derivational possibilities of the Russian language, mainly word formation. Being terms, the units of the language of hydraulic engineering have strictly defined meanings, however, many of them retain traces of semantic connections with prototerm and words that served as derivational material. The "older" the scope of the term, the more complex and multifaceted these connections.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The study of hydro-technical terms showed that the process of formation of terminological units is complex, takes place in several stages and in different sequences, for example: from a word to a term (river); from term to word (fountain). A common word may eventually begin to be used as a proto-term, while a common etymon may remain in the language (river) or disappear. Derivation (water intake) is also actively taking place, however, the borrowing of terms (gateway) is not the main source of replenishment of the hydro-technical terminology.

The complexity of the hydraulic engineering industry has determined the special structure of the term system, which is a polycentric structure consisting of partially intersecting term fields. The presence of several term fields intersecting in the nuclear or peripheral areas creates a system with several semantic centers or nuclei, which we propose to call polycentric. Another feature of the system of hydraulic engineering terms should be called the blurring of the boundaries of the semantic fields that form it: the same unit can simultaneously refer to different industry term fields of hydraulic engineering, while the meaning of the term can vary: a swamp - an ecosystem (ecology), a swamp - a water body (hydrology).), a swamp - a piece of land (geography).

In addition to terminological use, the word swamp is used in the general literary language both in direct and figurative meaning, which is also accompanied by negative connotations. The frequency of such units, which, along with the commonly used terminological meaning, is high in hydraulic engineering, which is primarily due to the history of the industry, which developed in accordance with the local landscape. The derivational analysis revealed that the term system of hydraulic engineering is replenished mainly due to the own word-formation resources of the language and the number of borrowings in this term system is relatively small. The selection and analysis of vocabulary related to the specialty "Hydraulic Engineering" made it possible to form an educational thesaurus as the basis for the texts and exercises of the textbook for foreign students. The process of teaching professional communication within the framework of teaching a foreign language in hydro-technical construction field is focused on the terms and terminological systems of the specialty language, on the basis of which programs are compiled and educational material is formed. The systematization of the vocabulary that functions in this area is a necessary step in the preparation of a textbook in the Russian language for foreigners studying the specialty "Hydraulic

Engineering". The analysis of the system of hydro-technical terms is important and has practical significance.

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